

Phenomenological Velocity and the Inertia Cobordism

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1 Background

Let $\pi : E \rightarrow B$ be a fiber bundle such that $dom(W) = B$ and $codom(W) = E$ where $W \supseteq M \stackrel{\sim}{\leftrightarrow} M'$, with $M = \sqcup_i M_i$ and $M' = \sqcup_j M'_j$ covering antipodal points on the boundary of a manifold $\mathcal{M}$. Then, W is a bordism, and specifying a choice of W is equivalent to specifying a choice of paths between cobordant collars.

Let $\mathcal{W} \supset W$, and let $\partial\mathcal{W} \supset \{M, M'\}$. Let G be a finite group. Then, there is an obvious left action $\partial\mathcal{W} \times g = \theta Proj(\alpha)$, where $\alpha \in W$. That is to say, if $\phi : \alpha \rightarrow \partial\mathcal{W}$ is a projective morphism, then g acts on either M or M' by rotation, and $\theta \in [0, 2\pi] \simeq S^1$.

Consider a simply connected path γ , of length $\mathbf{len}(\mathcal{W})$; that is to say,

$$span(\gamma) = span(\mathcal{W})$$

Consider a chart $\rho = (\mathcal{U}, \alpha, \beta)$ containing a particle represented by α , and a second particle whose state is correlated to α , such that $\alpha \propto \beta$, so that for some time t , any measure of α will become a measure of β . We can think of γ as a string whose Hamiltonian ends on 2-branes at the collars of a cobordism, with our particles lying somewhere along this string. The probability of $\gamma \cap x$ being non-empty for some $x = d(\gamma, \gamma')$ can be approximated by the wave-function of $\alpha \wedge \beta|_{t=t^\circ}$ where t° is the time at which $\mu(\alpha) = \mu(\beta)$ for $\mu(\bullet)$ some deterministic measure of $\bullet$.

Suppose $\mu(\bullet) = v(\bullet)$ is the velocity of the measured particle with respect to some inertial frame of reference ρ^+ . Then,

$$\left. \frac{d^2 d(\bullet, \bullet')}{d^2 t} \right|_{t=t^\circ} \text{ is fixed}$$

In other words, the phenomenological velocity $v(\bullet)|_{\rho^+}$ is completely deterministic with respect to the correspondence $\alpha \propto \beta$.

2 Relativity

Let there be two group actions, $g, g' = \theta Proj(\alpha), \theta' Proj(\alpha)$, with $\theta' \in (0, \pi) \bmod(\pi)$ and $\theta \in 0 \bmod(\pi)$ or $\theta \in \pi \bmod(\pi)$. Write these actions by g_1 and g_0 , respectively. Then we have that, for $(\beta \times \alpha) = \mathbf{false}$, g_1 is an action on β if $\beta \not\sim \alpha$.

Let $\gamma(\bullet)$ be the path spanning $\mathcal{W}$ associated with $\bullet$. Then, the path $\gamma(\alpha)$ is the shortest timewise path, and the path $\gamma(\beta)$ will appear length contracted.

Thus, $\mu(\mathbf{len}(\gamma(\alpha))) < \mu(\mathbf{len}(\gamma(\beta)))$ from an inertial observer centered at the origin of $dom(W)$. Let $\iota = \mathbf{len}(\gamma(\beta)) - \mathbf{len}(\gamma(\alpha))$. Then,

$$\lim_{\mathbf{len}(\gamma(\alpha)) \rightarrow \infty} \iota = 0$$

assuming $\infty - \infty = 0$.

Using Emmerson's energy numbers, we rewrite 0 by $\nu_{\mathbb{E}} \in \mathbb{E}$. Thus, we have

$$\lim_{\iota \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d\iota}{dt} = \nu_{\mathbb{E}} + 1$$

Let $\mathfrak{Z}$ be a $\mathbb{Z}$ -graded module acting on a topological space $\mathcal{O} := \mathfrak{Z}/g$ with an orbifold structure. Let $Hol_{\alpha}^{\mathcal{G}}$ be the holonomy groupoid of a particle represented by α .

Theorem 2.1. $\exists g \in \mathcal{G} \times g \in G$

Proof. We have

$$\sqcup_{i,j} \mathfrak{g}_{i,j} \alpha = \sqcup_{j,i} g_{j,i} \alpha$$

which shows that the sub-object identifier $i : j$ has the same index as $j : i$, and thus, the actions are correlated. $\square$

The group G acts from the right on α , while the group $\mathcal{G}$ acts from the right on $Proj(\Psi(\alpha))$. The commutator $[i, j]$ maps $\Psi(\alpha)$ to α by the map $f(\tilde{\alpha})$, which, together with $\mathcal{U}(\tilde{\alpha})$, forms a uniformizing system for α . $Hol_{\alpha}^{\mathcal{G}}$ is then a collection of maps

$$\{\rho^{-1}(\alpha) \rightarrow \rho(\alpha) \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \rho^{-1^n}(\alpha)\}$$

and we obtain a short exact sequence

$$\nu_{\mathbb{E}} \hookrightarrow \Psi(\alpha) \twoheadrightarrow \alpha \twoheadrightarrow Proj(\alpha) \twoheadrightarrow \nu_{\mathbb{E}}$$

Notice, the first map is an inclusion, but we successively restrict ourselves at every other level until we obtain our zero object.

Suppose there is a one-to-one bijection between the elements of $\Psi(\alpha)$ and the elements of $\gamma(\alpha)$. Then, $v(\alpha)$ is simply a forgetful functor: $res_0 : \Psi(\alpha) \xrightarrow{\sim} \iota$. That is to say, the relative (phenomenological) velocity of α is a *categorical* construction. Namely, it is a map from the large category of ∞ -categories, to the small category of 1-categories with embeddings into the real numbers. So, for a generic measurement $\mu(\alpha)$, we obtain a map $\mathbb{E} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, where the prime ideals of $\mathbb{E}$ are localized at a real number.